

MANAGEMENT IN NURSING

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Abstract: *Fundamentals of management Changes in the political and economic life of the country, the development of democratic principles in the management of production require in-depth study of modern methods and forms of management by managers and employees of medical institutions.*

Key words: *nursing, management, medicine*

Management is the process of continuously influencing the object of management, expressing the meaning of management and spending less time and effort to achieve effective results on a large scale. Management is an old art and a new science. Governance is an integral part of the political, economic, technological, social and ethical systems and has its own direction, principles and style. The fundamentals of governance in the health care system also have their own characteristics. For example, target management:

develop a clear, concise goal;

develop clear plans and achieve them;

continuous monitoring and determination of work and results;

take new measures to achieve the planned results.

Governance is now a key factor in the development of society. Today:

governance is the general and primary task of modern society;

the main task of management is the effectiveness of knowledge;

management is not only a business activity, but also a wealth of culture and system;

governance is a product of human activity and at the same time a universal problem;

governance builds economic and social development. Basic scientific principles of management:

orderly approach to management;

defining the purpose of management;

use of material and moral methods of motivating employees;

Management in the health care system is a kind of governance in which the main goal of health care organizations is to protect people's health and thus improve public health. Population health is the basis of national wealth, with a portion of national income allocated to health care, but health is also "used" as a reserve to create material wealth. In general, life expectancy can be a key indicator of a country's economy, the efficiency of the national economy. This should be taken into account when evaluating the effectiveness of health management.

Principles of health care management:

the goals of health system organizations are different from the goals of other sectors, and the process differs not only in difficulty but also in summarizing the results.

in health care organizations, because the control over the activities of their employees is very low (this applies to doctors), the staff of the administrative institution should focus on the quality of medical services, not the quantity.

the distinguishing feature of the health care system from other areas is the high specialization of the medical staff, as well as the interdependence of different groups of specialists. Therefore, it is important to know not only the science and practice of health management, but also the basics of medical knowledge.

Managers are people with a certain level of responsibility. No matter what the organization, they have a big role to play in governance.

Management is an active person who directs projects, programs and organizational work, acting according to certain rules and conditions.

Manager - managerial responsibilities:

management, leadership, interpersonal relationships;

verification and dissemination of information, general expression of ideas;

decision-making, business, chaos elimination, resource allocation, negotiation.

Management consists of three levels:

primary lower level - is a senior nurse who directly supervises subordinates;

mid-level management - is the management of the senior nurse of the institution, which has the right to supervise and direct the activities of lower-level employees;

top management is the person who is responsible for all the important issues that are addressed in the institution, i.e. the physician of the institution. His task is to select staff, improve their skills, regroup them.

Responsibilities: Managing nurses, monitoring their activities, including maintaining and supporting their professionalism. So, a manager is a qualified manager, a person who strives for innovation.

There are three types of office work:

a highly critical manager - one who had sufficient authority over the workers to pass judgment;

a democratic ruler who tries not to pass judgment;

a free agent is a person who does his job

References:

1. M.F.Ziyayeva. Z.O.Rizayeva. "Bolalarda hamshiralik parvarishi". Toshkent, "Fan va texnologiya" 2012 yil.
2. X.N Fayziyev. « Сестринский уход за детьми » Toshkent, «Ilm ziyo» nashriyoti, 2008 yil
3. K.S Inomov. «Pediatriyada hamshiralik ishi» Toshkent, 2007 yil
4. www.ziyonet.uz
5. <https://mymedic.uz/>